

MOONIS: THE SPECTROMETER ON RASHID ROVER TO EXPLORE THE LUNAR SOUTH POLAR REGIONS. De Sanctis¹ M.C., F. Altieri¹, D. Biondi¹, S. De Angelis¹, L. Rossi¹, M. Ciarniello¹, M. Ferrari¹, G. Filacchione¹, M. Formisano¹, A. Frigeri¹, V. Galluzzi¹, A. Raponi¹, E. Ammannito², R. Pepe², J. Regolini³, ¹INAF/IAPS, Via Del Fosso Del Cavaliere 100, 00133, Rome, Italy (mariaacristina.desanctis@inaf.it), ²Agenzia Spaziale Italiana, Via del Politecnico snc 00133 Rome Italy, ³ Agenzia Spaziale Italiana, Località Terlecchia 75100 Matera, Italia, ³Leonardo Company, Via Delle Officine Galileo, 1, 50013 Campi Bisenzio FI.

Introduction: The MoonIS instrument is a VIS-IR spectrometer onboard the Emirates Lunar Mission (ELM) of the Mohammed Bin Rashid Space Centre (MBRSC). The mission is part of the MBRSC lunar exploration program and involves the development and launch of the series of "Rashid" lunar rovers. The mission Rashid Rover 3 has the target of exploring the lunar South Pole region, with the main objectives of:

- Studying the geographic and geological features of the lunar polar region
- Investigating the presence of water in the lunar polar region
- Analyzing the geological characteristics of the lunar South Pole, examining the surface properties and composition of the soil.
- Exploring the Permanent Shadowed Region (PSR) in the lunar South Pole
- Studying the presence of water in the southern polar region, identifying ice and hydroxyl on the surface and under the surface.

MoonIS spectrometer, a heritage of the MA_MISS instrument on board the Rosalind Franklin rover of the ESA ExoMars mission [1], is part of the scientific payload on board the Rashid lunar rover. The launch of the mission is scheduled for 2028.

Lunar PSRs: The lunar PSRs are expected to host large quantities of water-ice, which are key for sustainable exploration of the Moon and beyond [2-4]. However, only limited information is available about fine-scale geomorphology and distribution of ice within PSRs because the orbital imagery obtained to date lacks sufficient resolution and/or signal. Characterizing water ice in the PSRs is a primary goal of lunar science and exploration. Permanently shadowed regions on the Moon and other solar system bodies (e.g. Mercury and Ceres) act as cold traps for the accumulation of water ice and other volatiles, which are thought to have been released over time by impacts of comets, asteroids, or even possible outgassing and interaction of the surface with the solar wind. The origin of water ice in the PSRs through the solar system is not clear and the study of lunar PSRs could help understanding the history of volatiles on the lunar surface and on other planetary bodies. Furthermore, it is not clear how much water ice on the Moon is exposed since from a morphological point of view it does not present the expected characteristics. In situ investigations are

therefore essential to better understand the nature of the ice and its amount. For this reason, several space agencies are planning to send rovers to better investigate water-ice and overall surface composition within PSRs and pave the way for human exploration.

The MoonIS instrument: The MoonIS instrument is designed to obtain spectra of the lunar surface in the 0.4-2.3 μm range. The MoonIS spectrometer design is inherited from the Ma_MISS instrument aboard the ESA's ExoMars Rosalind Franklin Rover with changes in the optical head, calibration target, thermomechanical, and electronics design. In particular, MoonIS Optical Head (OH) will be mounted on the rover mast and connected through optical fibers to the spectrometer housed on the rover. Each fiber is coupled to a dedicated optical element in the OH to allow to observe the scene while the other end is coupled to the spectrometer's slit. This configuration allows to disperse the signal of each fiber across multiple pixels on a detector. The resulting hyperspectral image consists of the same number of "spots" on the detector as the number of fibers that will be accommodated and which are acquired simultaneously. The area in front and surrounding the rover is scanned with the rover mast that will allow to investigate the entire region of interest. Using this concept, MoonIS will acquire consecutive or not consecutive images of multiple "pseudo-pixels", thanks to the mast and rover movements. An external Calibration target for radiometric and spectral calibration of the MoonIS instrument is also being considered. MoonIS will be equipped with an illumination system, capable to illuminate the region of interest in the PSRs.

Main scientific objectives: The instrument is designed to achieve high-quality, advanced scientific results in characterizing the composition of the lunar surface. A key focus is the identification, distribution, and analysis of water ice, one of the mission's primary objectives. The main goals can be summarized as follows:

- identify and distinguish H_2O and OH;
- evaluate the amount of H_2O and OH and their distribution;
- recognize the main class of lunar rocks;
- identify and quantify different minerals (e.g. pyroxenes, olivines, feldspars, spinels, etc.);

- identify different mixtures and determine their spatial distribution.

MoonIS characteristics in terms of S/N, spectral resolution, range, and spatial resolution are suitable to achieve the above mentioned goals both in the sun-illuminated regions and in the PSR, the primary focus of the mission.

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References: [1] De Sanctis et al. (2017) (2017): *Astrobiology* 17, 6, 7. [2] McCubbin et al. (2015) *American Mineralogist* 100: 1668-1707. [3] Honniball et al. (2021) *Nature Astronomy* 5: 121-127. [4] Pieters et al. (2009) *Science*, 326, 568–572.